

Curriculum Vitae

Devendra Adhikari

Personal Details

- **Name:** Devendra Adhikari
- **Date of Birth:** January 17, 1969 (2025/10/4)
- **Address:** Biratnagar Metropolitan City, Ward No.-1, Morang, Nepal
- **Affiliations:** Dept. of Physics, Mahendra Morang Adarsh Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University, Biratnagar, Nepal.
- **Contact:** Dept. of Physics, Mahendra Morang Adarsh Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University, Biratnagar, Nepal.
- **Email:** devendra.adhikari@mmamc.tu.edu.np ; deven.bmhs@gmail.com
Cell: 9842028969 / 9805377285
- **Url:** https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=_RrUzFEAAAAJ&hl=en

Professional Experience

- **Professor:** April, 2013 to Present
- **Associate Professor:** August, 2009 to April, 2013
- **Assistant Professor:** June, 2000 to August, 2009
- **Asst. Lecturer:** August, 1996 to June 2000

Education

- **Ph.D.:** T. M. Bhagalpur University, India, 2012
Thesis title: Regular associated solution models for the properties of binary liquid alloys.
Supervisor: Prof. B.P. Singh
Date of Ph. D. Award: March 29, 2012
- **M. Sc.:** Tribhuvan University, Nepal, 1993
- **B. Sc.:** Tribhuvan University, Nepal, 1991
- **I. Sc.:** Tribhuvan University, Nepal, 1988

Research Supervision

- Ph. D.: 6 students (completed), 1 student (ongoing)
- M. Sc. Dissertation: 26 students (completed)
- B. Sc. project supervision: 40 students

Research Projects Completed

- **Principal Investigator**, "Thermodynamic and Surface Properties of Liquid Al-Cu-Ni Alloys" and "Assessment of Thermophysical Properties of Al-Mg-Si Liquid Alloys" (2023), in collaboration with Dr. Rada Novakovic, ICMATE-CNR, Italy. (*One study published in "Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance," another communicated to "Physica B: Condensed Matter"*)
- **Co-Investigator**, "Structural, Electronic, Optical, Magnetic, and Mechanical Properties of Perovskite" (July 2023 – July 2024), in collaboration with Sikkim Manipal Institute of Technology, India. (*Output submitted to AIP Advances*)
- **Principal Investigator**, Faculty Research Grant 2017: "Study of Surface Tension, Viscosity and Structural Properties of Binary Liquid Alloys" (Successfully completed, presented on Nov 30, 2020, final report Jan 17, 2021). (*University Grants Commission*)
- **Team Leader/Principal Investigator**, Research Grant: "Properties of Liquid Alloys" (2012 / Fiscal Year 2068/069). (*Nepal Academy of Science & Technology - NAST, completed April 21, 2013*)
- **Team Leader/Principal Investigator**, Faculty Research Grants-2013: "Mixing Behaviour of Liquid Alloys" (Successfully completed, final report Dec 6, 2013). (*University Grants Commission*)
- **Team Leader/Principal Investigator**, Research Grant: "Properties of Liquid Alloys" (2014 / Fiscal Year 2068/069). (*Nepal Academy of Science & Technology - NAST, completed April 21, 2015*)

Editorial Experiences

- Editor-in-Chief: BIBECHANA (A Two Star Journal), 2011-Present
- Editor-in-Chief: The Journal of Knowledge and Innovation, 2022-Present

Awards, Scholarships and Honors

- Best Teacher Award (2079) MMAMC, Biratnagar
- Nepal Vidya Bhusan "Ka"
- University Grant Commission fellowship for Ph.D.
- Max James Clerk Award, UK-2011 (Nominated for Best Author)
- Travel grant from INASP, UK
- Grant for visiting ICTP, Italy as Guest Scientist
- Travel grant from UGC for conference attendance in Germany

Conference/Workshop

- Workshop on Research Methodology for Faculty, Organized by MMAMC, TU, Biratnagar (May 28-30, 2025) -**Lead Facilitator**
- Workshop on Practical Examination of Physics, Mech Multiple Campus, Bhadrapur, Nepal (February 29 - March 1, 2024 / B.S. 2080/11/17-18) - **Subject Expert Facilitator**
- Faculty Capacity Enhancement (FCE) Program organized by Institute of Science and Technology, TU (April 29-May 5, 2024/B. S. 2081/01/17-23)-**Facilitator**
- "Supporting and Strengthening Capacity Building for Teachers" Training - "Scientific Publication and Copyright", Central Campus of Technology, Dharan (May 1-5, 2024 / B.S. 2081/02/18-22) - **Subject Expert**
- Journal Editing and Management Training (Organized by Research Directorate, TU), Central Library, TU, Kathmandu (September 21-22, 2023 / B.S. 2080/06/04-05) – **Lead Facilitator**
- Journal Editing Training (Organized by ODEC, TU), Yellow Pagoda Hotel, Kathmandu (May 22-23, 2023 / B.S. 2080/02/08-09) – **Lead Facilitator**
- Workshop on Academic Writing for Faculty, Organized by MMAMC, TU, Biratnagar (August 21-23, 2023) -**Lead Facilitator**
- Workshop on Editor’s Training for Journal Editors, Organized by RMC, Biratnagar Nursing Campus, TU, Biratnagar (May 22-23, 2023)-**Lead Facilitator**
- Journal Management Training, (Organized by ODEC, TU), Yellow Pagoda Hotel, Kathmandu (December 3-5, 2022 / B.S. 2079/08/17-19), **Participant**
- INASP Workshop on Improving Journal Quality and Publishing on NepJOL, Tribhuvan University Central Library (November 3-5, 2014), -**Participant**
- International Conference on Emerging Trends on Science and Technology, Biratnagar, Nepal (March 22-23, 2014)-**Convener and Paper Presenter**
- International Conference on Material Science and Condensed Matter Physics, Berlin, Germany (May 22-23, 2013) - **Presented a scientific paper**
- Seminar on Modern Trends in Science and Technology, Biratnagar, Nepal (December

28-29, 2012) – *Convener and Presented a scientific paper*

- 1st International Science Congress (ISC-2011), Indore, MP, India (December 24-25, 2011) -*Presented a scientific paper*
- AuthorAID @ INASP Training Workshop on Research Writing Skills, Kathmandu, Nepal (March 14-17, 2011), -*Participant*
- AuthorAID @ INASP Train the Trainers Workshop, Kathmandu, Nepal (March 18, 2011),-*Participant*
- Regional Chemistry Seminar, Biratnagar, Nepal (June 7-8, 2011), *Keynote Speaker*
- International Conference on Frontiers of Physics, Kathmandu, Nepal (June 2-5, 2009), *Paper Presenter*
- Teaching Skill Improvement Training, Kathmandu, Nepal (September 13-23, 1999), - *Participant*
- Online Teaching & Learning Activities Coordination Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar (Formed B.S. 2077/06/05)-*Coordinator*

Workshop/Seminar Organized

- AuthorAID Workshop on Research Writing and Publishing, 29th-30th July, 2011, Biratnagar, Nepal (*Chief Facilitator*) - Program was supported by INASP, UK.
- Seminar on Modern Trends in Science and Technology, December 28-29, 2012, Biratnagar, Nepal, *Conference Secretary and Editor*
- International Conference on Emerging Trends on Science and Technology, March 22-23, 2014, Biratnagar, Nepal, *Conference Convener and Editor*

Major Administrative Experiences

- **Chairman:** Purbanchal University Service Commission, Gothgaun, Sundarharaich (January, 2026-May, 2026)
- **Head of Department:** Dept. of Physics, Mahendra Morang Adarsh Multiple Campus, Biratnagar (July 2023-Janury 2026)
- **Chairperson:** Research Management Cell, Mahendra Morang A. M. Campus, Biratnagar (January, 2023- January, 2026)

- **Coordinator:** Strategic Planning Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (July, 2019-July, 2020)
- **Coordinator:** Department Research Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (August, 2019-August, 2022)
- **Coordinator:** Self-Assessment Team, MMAMC, Biratnaga, TU (June, 2019-January, 2026)
- **Coordinator:** M.Sc. Physics, MMAMC, Birathagar, TU (August, 2018-August, 2021)
- **Coordinator:** Science Research Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (June, 2018- June, 2020)
- **Coordinator:** EMIS Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (May, 2018-May, 2020)
- **Coordinator:** Library Management Committee, Western Region Campus, Tribhuvan University, Pokhara, (December, 1997-December,1999)
- **Coordinator:** Journal Publishing Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (April 3, 2023- January, 2026)
- **Focal Person:** EMIS Unit MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (May, 2018-May, 2020)
- **Member:** Selection Committee, B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan (August, 2015-August, 2018)
- **Member:** Karyabidhi of Dean, Assit. Dean, and other appointments, Purbanchal University (September, 2020)
- **Member:** Standing Committee, Academic Council, Purbanchal University (2023)
- **Member:** Academic Council, Purbanchal University (August, 2020-August, 2023)
- **Member:** Faculty Board, Tribhuvan University (April 17, 2019-April 16, 2021)
- **Member:** Campus Management Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (April, 2019-August, 2025)
- **Member:** Campus Executive Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (April, 2019- August, 2025)
- **Member:** Curriculum Development Committee, Open University Development Committee (August, 2015-August, 2017)
- **Member:** Subject Committee, Physics, Tribhuvan University (December, 2014-December, 2023)
- **Member Secretary:** IQAC, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (July 4, 2019- January, 2026)
- **Member:** Science Working Committee, MMAMC, Birathagar, TU (August, 2018- August, 2021)
- **Member:** B. Sc. CSIT, BIT and M.Sc. Physics Working Committee, MMAMC, Biratnagar, TU (December, 2014 – December, 2017)
- **Member:** B. E. Coordination Committee, Western Region Campus, TU Pokhara (July, 1999- July, 2001)

- **Member:** Diploma Full-fee Management Committee, Western Region Campus, Tribhuvan University, Pokhara (August, 1998-August, 2001)
- **Member:** Advisory Board, Western Region Campus, Tribhuvan University, Pokhara (December, 1998-December, 1999)
- **Hostel Warden:** Western Region Campus, Tribhuvan University, Pokhara Committee, December, 1997-December, 1999

Other Affiliations

- Chairman - Nepal Physical Society, Koshi Province
- Life Member - Nepal Physical Society
- Indian Physics Congress Association - Member

Publications

Peer-Review International Journals

1. First-principles study of electronic, vibrational, elastic and thermodynamic properties of Sc-X (X= C, N, O) compounds
SK Yadav, S Dahal, R Khadka, B Guragain, P Pokharel, P Oli, **D Adhikari**
Pramana 100 (2) 53, 2026
2. Theoretical Assessment of Binary Pair Interactions Affecting the Thermodynamic and Surface Properties of Al-Cu-Fe-Ti Melt and Its Ternary Subsystems
DK Sah, U Mehta, **D Adhikari**, SK Yadav
Journal of Phase Equilibria and Diffusion, 1-15, 2026
3. A Highly Sensitive and Selective Sb-Doped MoS₂ Monolayer in Detecting Toxic Gases: Insight From DFT and NEGF
P Oli, B Chettri, RP Adhikari, **D Adhikari**, B Sharma, SK Yadav
Engineering Reports 8 (1) e70590, 2026
4. Modeling thermodynamic, surface, and viscous properties of Bi-In-Sn melt
N Dahal, SK Yadav, RP Koirala, RK Gohivar, U Mehta, **D Adhikari**
AIP Advances, 15 (9), 2025
5. First Principles Study of Electronic, Vibrational, Elastic, and Thermodynamic Properties of Sc-X (X = P, S, Se) Compounds
SK Yadav, S Dahal, R Khadka, B Guragain, P Pokharel, P Oli, **D Adhikari**
Engineering Reports, 7(1) e13115, 2025
6. Theoretical assessment of thermodynamic and surface properties of Ag-Al-Au-Cu liquid alloy at different temperatures
DK Sah, U Mehta, RK Gohivar, **D Adhikari**, SK Yadav
Applied Physics A 131 (2) 144, 2025
7. Thermodynamic, Surface and Viscous Properties of Cu-Fe-Ti Alloys in Liquid State Based on Exponential Temperature-Dependent Interaction Energy Parameters
U Mehta, DR Yadav, SK Yadav, **D Adhikari**
Journal of Phase Equilibria and Diffusion, 1-12, 2025

8. Thermodynamic, structural and surface properties of Cd-Na alloys in liquid state
U Mehta, I Bharati, **D Adhikari**
Journal of Phase Equilibria and Diffusion 46 (1) 91-99, 2025
9. Mixing behaviour of Al–Ga–Mg alloys in liquid state at different temperatures
A Dhungana, SK Yadav, U Mehta, R Novakovic, **D Adhikari**
Philosophical Magazine, 105 (13)716-738, 2025
10. Elastic Anisotropy and Thermal Properties of Sr₂ZrMoO₆ Double Perovskite under Different Pressure
P Pokharel, SK Yadav, N Pantha, B Sharma, **D Adhikari**
physica status solidi (b) 262 (5) 2400625, 2025
11. First-Principles Investigations of Structural, Electronic, and Elastic Properties of ZrSiO₃ Perovskite: Layer Dependence, Surface Termination, and Pressure Effects
P Pokharel, SK Yadav, N Pantha, **D Adhikari**
*physica status solidi (b)*261 2400156, 2024
12. Assessment of thermophysical properties of Al–Mg–Si liquid alloys A Dhungana, SK Yadav, RK Gohivar, R Novakovic, **D. Adhikari**
Physica B: Condensed Matter, 688, 416160, 2024
13. Strain-dependent electronic, mechanical and piezoelectric properties of ZrSiO₃ 2D monolayer: A first principle approach
P Pokharel, SK Yadav, N Pantha, **D Adhikari**
Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids, 193, 112198, 2024
14. Thermodynamic and Surface Properties of Liquid Al-Cu-Ni Alloys A Dhungana, S Yadav, U Mehta, R Novakovic, **D Adhikari**
Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance, 1-11, 2023
15. Thermodynamic, surface and viscous properties of ternary Al–Fe–Mn alloy using theoretical modellings
U Mehta, SK Yadav, I Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids 60 (1) 111-128, 2022
16. Temperature-dependent mixing behaviours of Bi-Mg liquid alloys
IB Bhandari, I Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids 59 (6) 918-931, 2021
17. Thermodynamic, surface and transport properties of ternary Al–Sn–Zn liquid alloy and its sub binaries
RK Gohivar, U Mehta, SK Yadav, RP Koirala, IS Jha, **D Adhikari** *Philosophical Magazine* 101 (11) 1380-1399, 2021
18. Study of excess free energy of mixing and heat of mixing of liquid ternary Al–Li–Zn alloy by assessing the thermodynamic properties of sub-binary alloys
RK Gohivar, SK Yadav, RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Physica B: Condensed Matter 610, 412941, 2021
19. Phase segregating and complex forming Pb-based (= X-Pb) liquid alloys
IB Bhandari, N Panthi, I Koirala, **D Adhikari**

20. Study of artifacts in thermodynamic and structural properties of Li–Mg alloy in liquid state using linear and exponential models
RK Gohivar, SK Yadav, RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Heliyon 7 (3) e06613, 2021
21. Optimization of thermodynamic and surface properties of ternary Ti–Al–Si alloy and its sub- binary alloys in molten state
SK Yadav, U Mehta, **D Adhikari**
Heliyon 7 (3) e06511, 2021
22. Thermodynamic and surface properties of Al–Li–Mg liquid alloy
A Dhungana, SK Yadav, **D Adhikari**
Physica B: Physics of Condensed Matter 598, 2020
23. Study of surface tension and viscosity of Cu–Fe–Si ternary alloy using a thermodynamic approach
U Mehta, SK Yadav, I Koirala, RP Koirala, GK Shrestha, **D Adhikari**
Heliyon 6 (8) e04674, 2020
24. Artifacts in Al–Mn liquid alloy
RK Gohivar, SK Yadav, RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Physica B: Physics of Condensed Matter 595, 412348, 2020
25. Mixing properties of Cu–Mg liquid alloy
SK Yadav, M Gautam, **D Adhikari**
AIP Advances 10 (12) 125320, 2020
26. Thermo-physical properties of ternary Al–Cu–Fe alloy in liquid state
U Mehta, SK Yadav, I Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Philosophical Magazine, 100(19)(2020) 2417–2435
27. Assessment of thermo-structural properties of Al-Fe and Fe-Si alloys at high temperatures
RK Gohivar, SK Yadav, RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids 59(5) 679–689, 2020
28. Thermodynamic and Surface Properties of Liquid Ti–Al–Fe Alloy at Different Temperatures
U Mehta, SK Yadav, I Koirala, RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids, 59(4) 585–596, 2020
29. Prediction of thermodynamic and surface properties of ternary Ti–Si–Fe liquid alloy
U Mehta, I Koirala, SK Yadav, RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**
Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering, 28 065010, 2020
30. Temperature dependence of interaction parameters of Cu–Si liquid alloy
RK Gohivar, RP Koirala, SK Yadav, **D Adhikari**
AIP Advances, 10, 085121, 2020
31. Prediction of thermodynamic and surface properties of Pb–Hg liquid alloys at different temperatures
SK Yadav, LN Jha, IS Jha, BP Singh, RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**

32. Theoretical assessment on mixing properties of liquid Tl–Na alloys
IS Jha, R Khadka, RP Koirala, BP Singh, **D Adhikari**
Philosophical Magazine 96 (16) 1664-1683, 2016
33. Mixing behaviour of Ni–Al melt at 1873 K
SK Yadav, S Lamichhane, LN Jha, NP Adhikari, **D Adhikari** *Physics and Chemistry of Liquids* 54 (3) 370-383, 2016
34. Thermodynamic and structural properties of Bi-based liquid alloys
SK Yadav, LN Jha, **D Adhikari**
Physica B: Condensed Matter 475, 40-47, 2015
35. Thermodynamic, structural and surface properties in Sn–Zn melt at 750 K BP Singh, RP Koirala, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
Applied Physics A 120 (4) 1347-1356, 2015
36. Segregating to ordering transformation in In–Sn melt
SK Yadav, LN Jha, **D Adhikari**
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids 53 (4) 443-454, 2015
37. Mixing behaviour of Au–Cu melt
R Kattel, D Gadtoula, RP Koirala, IS Jha, BP Singh, **D Adhikari**
Journal of the Chinese Advanced Materials Society 3 (3), 202-208, 2015
38. Thermo-physical properties of Mg–Tl melt
D Adhikari, SK Yadav, LN Jha
Journal of Basic and Applied Research International 9 (2) 103-110, 2015
39. Thermodynamic and Structural Behaviour of Mg–Ga Melt at 923
SK Yadav, LN Jha, **D Adhikari**
Journal of Advanced Physics 3 (3) 248-253, 2014
40. Concentration dependence of thermodynamic, transport and surface properties in Ag–Cu liquid alloys
IS Jha, I Koirala, BP Singh, **D Adhikari**
Applied Physics A 116 (3) 1517-1523, 2014
41. The segregating nature of Cd–Pb liquid binary alloys
BP Singh, I Koirala, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids 52 (4) 457-470, 2014
42. Thermo-physical properties of Al–Fe melt
D Adhikari, SK Yadav, LN Jha
Journal of the Chinese Advanced Materials Society 2 (3) 149-158, 2014
43. Bulk and surface properties of Co–Fe and Fe–Pd liquid alloys
RP Koirala, J Kumar, BP Singh, **D Adhikari**
Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids 394, 9-15, 2014
44. Thermodynamic, Surface and Viscous Properties of Molten Ga–Zn Alloys
RP Koirala, BP Singh, **D Adhikari**

45. Mixing properties of liquid Bi–Pb alloys
P Dahal, NK Rajbansi, **D Adhikari**
Journal of Molecular Liquids 191, 151-155, 2014
46. Theoretical investigations of mixing properties in Ni-Pd liquid alloys
I Koirala, BP Singh, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
ChemXpress 4 (1) 2014
47. Thermodynamic, transport and surface properties in In–Pb liquid alloys
I Koirala, IS Jha, BP Singh, **D Adhikari**
Physica B: Condensed Matter 423 49-53, 2013
48. Thermodynamic, Structural and Transport Properties of Molten Copper-Thallium Alloys
D Adhikari, RP Koirala, BP Singh
World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, International Journal ..., 2013
49. Thermodynamic, structural and surface properties of liquid Cd–Zn alloys
RP Koirala, BP Singh, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
Journal of Molecular Liquids 179, 60-66, 2013
50. Thermodynamic and structural behaviour of liquid Al-Ga alloys
RP Koirala, BP Singh, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
Adv Mat Lett 4, 283, 2013
51. Short range order in molten Al–Si alloys
BP Singh, **D Adhikari**, IS Jha
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids 50 (6) 697-704, 2012
52. Alloying behaviour of molten Ni–Pt and Al–Ge alloys
D Adhikari
Phase Transitions 85 (9) 824-830, 2012
53. Mixing properties of Al–Mg liquid alloy
D Adhikari, IS Jha, BP Singh
Indian Journal of Physics 86 (9) 783-786, 2012
54. Phase separation in Na–K liquid alloy
D Adhikari, BP Singh, IS Jha
Phase Transitions 85 (8) 675-680, 2012
55. Energetics of Cd-based binary liquid alloys
D Adhikari, BP Singh, IS Jha
Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids 358 (11) 1362-1367, 2012
56. Structural and energetic anomaly in liquid Na–Sn alloys
D Adhikari, BP Singh, IS Jha
Journal of Molecular Liquids 167, 52-56, 2012
57. Mixing behaviour of sodium-based liquid alloys
IS Jha, **D Adhikari**, BP Singh
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids 50 (2)199-209, 2012

58. Structural and energetic assessment in cadmium–indium liquid alloys
BP Singh, RP Koirala, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids, 1-8, 2012
59. Transport and surface properties of molten Al-Mn alloy
D Adhikari, IS Jha, BP Singh
Adv. Mat. Lett 3 (3) 226-230, 2012
60. Anomaly in mixing properties of lithium–magnesium liquid alloy
IS Jha, **D Adhikari**, J Kumar, BP Singh
Phase Transitions 84 (11-12) 1075-1083, 2011
61. Concentration dependence of thermodynamic properties of NaPb liquid alloy
BP Singh, J Kumar, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
World Journal of Condensed Matter Physics 2011, 2011
62. Alloying Behaviour of CuPd Liquid Alloy
BP Singh, **D Adhikari**, IS Jha, J Kumar, RP Koirala *Materials Sciences and Applications* 2 (08) 1139, 2011
63. Chemical ordering and thermodynamic properties of HgNa liquid alloys
D Adhikari, BP Singh, IS Jha, BK Singh
Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids 357 (15) 2892-2896, 2011
64. Disorder in liquid Cu–Pd alloys
D Adhikari
Phase Transitions 84 (4) 308-314, 2011
65. Inhomogeneity in structure of MgPb liquid alloy
D Adhikari
Physica B: Condensed Matter 406 (3) 445-448, 2011
66. Thermodynamic and structural investigations of liquid magnesium–thallium alloys
D Adhikari, IS Jha, BP Singh, J Kumar
Journal of Molecular Structure 985 (1) 91-94, 2011
67. Structural and energetic asymmetry in liquid Ag–Al alloys
D Adhikari, BP Singh, IS Jha
Physics and Chemistry of Liquids 48 (6) 787-796, 2010
68. Thermodynamic properties and microscopic structure of liquid Cd–Na alloys by estimating complex concentration in a regular associated solution
D Adhikari, BP Singh, IS Jha, BK Singh
Journal of Molecular Liquids 156 (2) 115-119, 2010
69. Concentration dependence of the structure and thermodynamic properties of silver–antimony alloys
BP Singh, **D Adhikari**, IS Jha
Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids 356 (33) 1730-1734, 2010
70. Structural asymmetry in liquid Fe–Si alloys
D Adhikari, IS Jha, BP Singh
Philosophical Magazine 90 (20) 2687-2694, 2010

71. Thermodynamic and microscopic structure of liquid Cu–Sn alloys
D Adhikari, IS Jha, BP Singh
Physica B: Condensed Matter 405 (7) 1861-1865, 2010

Peer-Review National Journals

1. Ab Initio Investigation of 1T-HfTe₂ Monolayer for Adsorption of SF₆ Decomposition Gases
P Oli, B Chettri, RP Adhikari, D Adhikari, B Sharma, S Yadav
Journal of Institute of Science and Technology 30 (2) 15-23, 2026
2. Machine Learning Model to Predict the Formation Energy of Copper-based Ternary Alloys
S Dahal, **D Adhikari**, SK Yadav
Journal of Institute of Science and Technology 29 (2) 99-105, 2025
3. Energetics and local order in In-based liquid alloys
RP Koirala, BP Singh, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
BIBECHANA 13, 60-71, 2015
4. Thermodynamic, structural, transport and surface properties of Pb-Tl liquid alloy
SK Yadav, LN Jha, **D Adhikari**
BIBECHANA 12, 20-29, 2014
5. Chemical ordering in In-Sn liquid alloy
D Adhikari
Nepal Journal of Science and Technology 14 (2) 161-164, 2014
6. Structural study of liquid Sn-Tl alloys
RP Koirala, IS Jha, BP Singh, **D Adhikari**
BIBECHANA 11, 46-52, 2014
7. Surface tension of two weakly interacting liquid alloys RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**, BP Singh
BIBECHANA 9, 103-112, 2012
8. Concentration Fluctuation in long Wavelength limit in liquid Magnesium Alloy
D Adhikari, BP Singh, IS Jha
Himalayan Physics 2 (2), 47-49, 2011
9. Complex formation in liquid potassium-lead alloy
BP Singh, **D Adhikari**, IS Jha, BK Singh
BIBECHANA 7, 1-5, 2011
10. Energy Disorder in Liquid Fe-Si Alloy
D Adhikari, IS Jha, BP Singh
Himalayan Physics 1, 37-40, 2010
11. Free Energy of Mixing and Activity of HgK Liquid Alloy
BP Singh, IS Jha, **D Adhikari**
BIBECHANA 6, 18-21, 2010
12. Experimental Study of Free Energy of Activation of Flow and Grunberg-Nissan

Parameters in Binary Liquid Mixtures

IS Jha, RP Koirala, **D Adhikari**

BIBECHANA 6, 9-14, 2010

Books Authored

- Physics for Engineering Students, M2M Publication, 2003
- Mathematical Physics for B.Sc. 3rd year, B and B Publication, 2007
- Fundamentals of Numerical Example in Physics, B and R Publication, 2010

Book Edited

- Modern Trends in Science and Technology, Biological and Physical Societies, 2013

Leadership & Governance Contributions

- Selection of employees in university
- Strategic planning for institutional development
- Leadership in academic governance and policy-making
- Examination system management & quality assurance
- Curriculum development and revision at national level
- Establishment and leadership of EMIS for transparency
- Quality Assurance & Accreditation (QAA) leadership
- Facilitated faculty development and research capacity programs

Professional Responsibilities

- Teaching in undergraduate and graduate level
- Supervision for Masters Dissertation
- Research Supervision for Ph. D. students
- Question Setting for examinations
- Updating curriculum as per need
- Students answer sheet checking
- Examination conducting
- Travel grant from UGC for conference attendance in India

Professional Summary

I am an experienced academician with nearly three decades of service in university governance, policy formulation, and institutional development. Throughout my career at Tribhuvan University, I have led

major committees related to strategic planning, quality assurance, examinations, EMIS, and faculty selection—promoting transparency, merit-based decisions, and accountable systems. With a strong record in institutional reform, evidence-based management, and fair recruitment practices, I am well prepared to contribute effectively as an academic leader in education, ensuring integrity, efficiency, and excellence in public service management.

Declaration

I hereby declare that all the information provided above is true and correct.

Prof. Devendra Adhikari

Date: 2083/01/18